

Examining How Platform-Based Digital Connection For Smes Affects Business Performance And How Environmental Instability Plays A Moderating Influence

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 29, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: May 30, 2023</p> <p>Keywords : Platform-based digital connection, Environmental instability, Moderating influence.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo. 8432566</p>	<p><i>Purpose – Small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) often operate in environments marked by high levels of turbulence. Such firms adopt digital technologies and platforms that provide access to external real-time information and establish digital connectivity between firms to remain competitive. This study aims to focus on SMEs' downstream and upstream platform-based digital connectivity (PDC).</i></p> <p><i>Design/methodology/approach–</i> <i>This study examines the effect of PDC on SMEs' operational performance under conditions of environmental turbulence. The data was gathered from 192 SMEs operating in the manufacturing arena in Pakistan.</i></p> <p><i>Findings–</i> <i>The results show that the adoption of PDC does not directly affect an SME's operational performance. However, in highly turbulent environments, PDC can improve operational performance. The results indicate that the performance effect of PDC varies according to the level and type of environmental turbulence.</i></p> <p><i>Research limitations/implications – This research offers insights into the relationship between PDC among SMEs and operational performance and encourages future research examining other possible conditional effects that could explain the contradictory results found in previous research.</i></p> <p><i>Originality/value– This study contributes to the knowledge of supply-chain digitalization among SMEs and its performance effects in varying environmental conditions. Further, this study contributes to the prior research by focusing on the interorganizational aspect of digitalization in SMEs.</i></p>

Introduction

The digitalization of small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) has recently attracted scholarly attention (Eller *et al.*, 2020; Matarazzo *et al.*, 2021; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021). The majority of the research exploring digital transformation has focused on large corporations (Cenamoret *et al.*, 2019; Matarazzo *et al.*, 2021), and it is argued that SMEs lag behind larger companies in terms of the extent of digitalization (Eller *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, SMEs compete in highly dynamic environments and continuously search for ways to survive, grow and be competitive (Cenamoret *et al.*, 2019; Lin and Lin, 2016; Martinelli and Tunisini, 2019). Digital technologies are developing and providing access to new ways to create value (deGooyert, 2020). The emergence of new digital technologies signals that firms should seek to transform their business digitally (Verhoef *et al.*, 2021). Many SMEs are making more use of digital platforms to implement their business strategies in response to the pressures of competition (Lietal., 2016). Prior research has reviewed the advantages of information technology for company performance (Eller *et al.*, 2020; Suoniemi *et al.*, 2022; Yunis *et al.*, 2018), but there remains little research on the impact of digitalization on firm performance (Eller *et al.*, 2020; Ferreira *et al.*, 2018). Results on the impact of digital technologies on firm performance are conflicting. Some studies report that using digital technologies alone does not benefit performance (Cenamoret *et al.*, 2019; Irani, 2010), and that a majority of projects adopting digital technology fail (Irani, 2010; Yunis *et al.*, 2018). However, some studies report positive effects on firm performance (Eller *et al.*, 2020; Li *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, it is feasible that the relationship between digitalization and firm performance is nonlinear (Kohtamäki *et al.*, 2020). These contradictory results demonstrate the existence of the productivity paradox of information technology (IT) (Brynjolfsson and Hitt, 1998). Digital technologies facilitate interactions between organizations, and digital platforms are an important source of competitive advantage in networked economies (Cenamoret *et al.*, 2019; Kazan *et al.*, 2018). Digitalization enhances effective interaction between firms and has made organizational boundaries more flexible and permeable (Corsaro and D'Amico, 2022). Moreover, digital technologies facilitate processes that connect people and companies and enable monitoring, communication, exchange and feedback (Cherbib *et al.*, 2021). Digital platforms and digital

technologies are forms of digital connectivity available to firms. Digital connectivity, which includes information sharing, is considered one of the most important contributors to expediting the flow of goods, mitigating risks and minimizing uncertainty in supply chains. The forms of digital connectivity available to firms include digital platforms and other digital technologies (Engelseth and Wang, 2018; Lin *et al.*, 2021b). This study focuses on platform-based digital connectivity (PDC), which refers to using digital technologies and processes in upstream and downstream supply chains to share information and convey knowledge. Prior research has argued that digital platforms are increasingly being created and implemented in various functions within supply chains (Lin *et al.*, 2021a).

Hypotheses of the study

H1. Platform-based digital connectivity has a negative effect on operational performance in SMEs.

H2. Environmental turbulence positively moderates the relationship between platform-based digital connectivity and a firm's operational performance.

H3. Competitive turbulence positively moderates the relationship between platform-based digital connectivity and a firm's operational performance.

H4. Technological turbulence positively moderates the relationship between PDC and a firm's operational performance.

H5. Market turbulence negatively moderates the relationship between PDC and operational performance.

Data collection and sample

The data were collected from SMEs operating in the manufacturing sector in Pakistan. In total, 1,136 manufacturing companies meeting a criterion of an annual turnover of 1.5–50m were selected from the Orbis database. Their CEOs were then invited to participate in the study via an internet-based survey constructed using the Webropol survey tool. In total, 21 of 720 companies completed the survey following an e-mail invitation. We sought to increase the response level by contacting 414 companies by telephone, and 323 then agreed to accept the survey, of which 172 eventually completed it, and 87 declined to participate. A total of 193 responses were received, including one duplicate submission. Therefore, the final sample comprises 192 SMEs, equating to a response rate of 17%, which can be considered adequate. The non-response bias was tested by comparing the turnover between non-respondents and respondents using a *t*-test. There were no differences between the groups $t(1109) = 0.477$, $p = 0.634$; hence, the sample appears representative of the selected population. Of the key respondents, 83% were CEOs, 4% were CFOs and 13% were in other management positions. The companies in the final sample are mainly small firms, in that 73% have fewer than 50 employees and 69% have a turnover of less than 10m. Among the sample, 59% of the companies operate in the metal manufacturing industry. The remaining 41% operate mostly in electric or electronic machinery, chemicals, petroleum, rubber, plastic, food or transport manufacturing industries.

Measures

PDC was measured through a novel instrument based on 20 items that interrogated the firms' digital connectivity. The measurement instrument was developed by three academics based on prior research on platform-based connectivity and tested by two practitioners – an IT professional and consultant and a CEO of a manufacturing SME. The items measure the PDC of a firm in both directions: upstream (suppliers) and downstream (customers) along the supply chain. All the PDC items were measured on a seven-point scale anchored with *not at all* (1) and *very much* (7). As the PDC measurement instrument is a novel one, we conducted several tests to assess the validity and reliability of the scale. First, we conducted an exploratory factor analysis that identified four factors. We named the dimensions of PDC to reflect the factors and thus categorized PDC into *digital supply chain transparency* (6 items), *digital product data* (2 items), *digitally enabled order-delivery process* (4 items) and *digital customer/supplier involvement* (6 items). The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.85, which exceeds the threshold value of 0.5. Further, the results of Bartlett's test of sphericity (2171.17, $p = 0.000$) also indicated that the data were suitable for factor analysis. Factor analysis was conducted with Oblimin rotation, and the four-factor solution explained 68% of the variance. Two items were dropped owing to low loadings. Next, the validity and reliability of those dimensions were reassessed. Although the digital supply chain transparency dimensions showed quite poor average variance extracted (AVE) values (< 0.5), the composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's alpha values exceeded the threshold values of 0.7. Research has accepted AVE values greater than 0.4 as adequate. We also assessed the discriminant validity of the measures through maximum shared variance (MSV) and average shared variance (ASV) values. The key criteria for assessing discriminant validity were that MSV was less than AVE and ASV was less than AVE. We concluded that the PDC constructs did not suggest any issues with discriminant validity. We also concluded that all the dimensions of PDC showed satisfactory validity and reliability. The relevant results are digital supply chain transparency (AVE = 0.43, CR = 0.82, $\alpha = 0.82$), digital product data (AVE = 0.59, CR = 0.74, $\alpha =$

0.74), digitally enabled order-delivery process (AVE = 0.58, CR = 0.85, α = 0.84) and digital customer/supplier involvement (AVE = 0.64, CR = 0.91, α = 0.92). Technological turbulence measures the speed and frequency of technological change, market turbulence is based on assessing the changes in customer preferences, and competitive turbulence measures the general degree of competition. Each of the three dimensions was measured by three items with a seven-point scale anchored with *totally disagree* (1) and *totally agree* (7). The assessment of the validity and reliability of the market turbulence scale revealed some issues relating to one item loading poorly, which adversely affected the AVE and CR values (AVE = 0.29, CR = 0.50, α = 0.48).

Table 1 Reliability and validity

Construct	CA	CR	AV	MS	AS
			E	V	V
<i>Platform-based digital connectivity</i>					
Digital supply chain transparency	0.82	0.82	0.43	0.42	0.31
Digital product data	0.74	0.74	0.59	0.27	0.27
Digitally enabled order-delivery process	0.84	0.85	0.58	0.41	0.27
Digital customer/supplier involvement	0.92	0.91	0.64	0.53	0.30
<i>Turbulence</i>					
Competitive turbulence	0.7	0.75	0.52	0.01	0.26
Market turbulence	0.5	0.48	0.29	0.50	0.26
Technological turbulence	0.84	0.85	0.65	0.50	0.26
<i>Operational performance</i>					
Delivery performance	0.84	0.82	0.53	0.02	0.17
Production costs	0.84	0.85	0.58	0.21	0.11
Product quality	0.87	0.88	0.78	0.48	0.14

Notes: CA = Cronbach's alpha; CR = Composite reliability; AVE = Average variance extracted; MSV = Maximum shared variance; ASV = Average shared variance.

Operational performance was measured through three dimensions: delivery performance (4 items), production costs (4 items) and product quality (2 items). Each of these dimensions was measured on a seven-point scale anchored with *totally disagree* (1) and *totally agree* (7). Delivery performance (AVE = 0.53, CR = 0.82, α = 0.84), production costs (AVE = 0.58, CR = 0.85, α = 0.84) and product quality (AVE = 0.78, CR = 0.88, α = 0.87) demonstrated acceptable levels of validity and reliability. The operational performance constructs did not have any discriminant validity issues. To ensure the validity of the operational performance measurement, we tested the relationship between the three-dimensional operational performance measure and objective performance indicators derived from the financial database. We found that our three-dimensional operational performance measure positively correlated with the EBIDTA margin of each company (0.15, $p < 0.05$), indicating the reliability of the subjective performance measure used. We also used company age, size and industry as control variables. Company age is a continuous variable. Company size was measured through turnover and dummy coded as 0 (turnover less than EUR 10m) or 1 (turnover over EUR 10m). The industry was dummy coded such that the metal industry was coded as 1 and other manufacturing as 0.

Test of measures

A confirmatory factor analysis was conducted using Stata 15.1 software to ensure the measurement model demonstrated sufficient validity. All items loaded significantly on their latent variables ($p < 0.000$), and the loadings ranged from 0.25 to 0.95. Although one item had a low loading (0.25), we decided to retain it in the measurement model, as it was part of a previously validated scale. All other loadings were acceptable. Although the loadings of two items fell below the 0.5 minimum loading recommended by Hair *et al.* (2014), they met the minimum criterion of 0.4 applied in other research (Kohtamäki and Partanen, 2016). The loadings and items are presented in Appendix. The fit indices indicate that the data fit the model well ($\chi^2/df = 1.69$; CFI = 0.91; TLI = 0.90; SRMR = 0.08; RMSEA = 0.06). These tests indicate that the measurement model is acceptable.

We used various tests to control for common method variance (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). First, we compared the research model to a single-factor model (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). The research model exhibits a significantly better model fit ($\chi^2/df = 1.69$; CFI = 0.91; TLI = 0.90; SRMR = 0.08; RMSEA = 0.06) than the single-factor model ($\chi^2/df = 4.71$; CFI = 0.41; TLI = 0.37; SRMR = 0.14; RMSEA = 0.14). The results suggest that common method variance is low. Second, we used the marker variable approach, which is suggested as an appropriate method for controlling the effects of common method variance (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). The technique incorporates a theoretically unrelated *marker variable* in the analysis; however, researchers rarely include unrelated

constructs in their surveys and tend to use a variable with a weak correlation with the main study variables (Richardson *et al.*, 2009). We chose a marker variable that was measured on a similar scale as the main study variables and thus was more likely to reflect the same method variance. We chose flexibility (consisting of three items) as our marker variable. It has a weak correlation with the turbulence and connectivity variables and is measurable on the same scale. It can therefore be assumed to have the same method variance effect as the other study variables. The common method variance analysis results show that the inclusion of the marker variable did not seriously affect the results because the relationships remained steady with and without the marker. Therefore, the tests indicate that common method variance is controlled for in the analysis and poses no threat to the interpretation of the study's results.

Analysis and results

The hypotheses were tested using moderated regression analysis employing State 15.1 software. Table 2 shows the correlations between constructs, means and standard deviations. The highest correlation between independent variables is 0.32 (Table 2), and the variance inflation factor (VIF) analysis shows that values for all constructs remain well below the threshold value of 10 (Hair *et al.*, 2014), as the highest VIF value is 1.12. The results indicate that multicollinearity is not an issue in the research model. We tested the research hypotheses through hierarchical regression analysis, the results are presented in Table 3. First, we tested the relationships between PDC and operational performance and the moderating effects of environmental turbulence. We ran a model including only the company age and industry control variables (Model 1), which were not found to have any effect on operational performance. Next, we added the direct effect of PDC and environmental turbulence to the model (Model 2). Environmental turbulence was found to have a positive relationship with operational performance ($b=0.22$, $p<0.001$). The moderation effect of environmental turbulence was added to the third model (Model 3), which is our main research model. The model shows that PDC is not directly associated with operational performance ($b = 0.03$, n.s.): *H1* is therefore unsupported. The model also provides evidence of the moderating role of environmental turbulence on the relationship between PDC and operational performance ($b=0.21$, $p<0.001$), which indicates that the relationship between PDC and operational performance varies according to the environmental conditions. The results demonstrate that in highly turbulent environments, PDC improves operational performance, while in the case of low turbulence, PDC reduces a firm's operational performance. Therefore, *H2* is supported. The moderation model explains 15% of the variance in the SMEs' operational performance, which is realistic, as operational performance comprises multiple effectual factors. We examined only the effects of PDC and environmental turbulence on performance.

Table 2 Correlations, means and standard deviations

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	4a	4b	4c			
	4d		5	6								
1. Company age	26.94	16.05										
2. Company size (1 = over 10 me)	0.32	0.47	0.09									
3. Industry (1 = metal industry)	0.59	0.49	-0.17 ^m	-0.03								
4. Platform-based digital connectivity	2.82	1.07	0.00	0.07	0.05							
4a. Digital supply chain transparency	2.44	1.18	0.00	0.10	-0.04							
4b. Digital product data	2.27	1.44	0.02	0.05	-0.02	0.47 ^{mmm}						
4c. Digitally enabled order-delivery process	3.60	1.60	-0.02	0.13	-0.06	0.55 ^{mmm}	0.37 ^{mmm}					
4d. Digital customer/supplier involvement	2.86	1.40	-0.00	-0.07	0.03	0.61 ^{mmm}	0.48 ^{mmm}	0.56 ^{mmm}				
5. Competitive turbulence	4.60	1.15	0.01	0.07	-0.18 ^m	0.06	-0.01	0.02	0.16 ^m			
6. Technological turbulence	3.54	1.32	-0.10	-0.01	0.07	0.32 ^{mmm}	0.24 ^{mmm}	0.24 ^{mmm}	0.24 ^{mmm}			
7. Operational performance	4.78	0.89	-0.05	0.05	-0.07	-0.00	0.2	-0.04	0.01	0.04	0.25 ^{mmm}	0.16 ^m

Notes: ^m $p \leq 0.05$, ^{mm} $p \leq 0.01$, ^{mmm} $p \leq 0.001$

Table 3 Results of the hierarchical regression analyses

	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
Industry: metal manufacturing			0.15		0.12	
Company size: over 10 me		-	0.11		0.11	
<i>Main effects</i>						
Platform-based digital connectivity (PDC)				-	0.07	0.03
Environmental turbulence			0.22 ^{mmm}		0.21 ^{mm}	
<i>Moderation effects</i>						
×PDC environmental turbulence					0.21 ^{mmm}	0.06
		0.01	0.04			
		0.01	0.05		0.15	
		0.00	0.04		0.12	
		0.78	5.44		5.51	

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Notes: ^mp < 0.05, ^{mm}p < 0.01, ^{mmm}p < 0.001

Figure 1 The moderating effect of environmental turbulence on the relationship between PDC and operational performance

moderating effect of environmental turbulence on the relationship between PDC and operational performance.

To extend our understanding of the moderating effects of environmental turbulence on the relationship between PDC and operational performance, we tested the different turbulence types separately (Table 4). The analysis indicates that the effects of competitive turbulence on operational performance were positively associated with operational performance ($b = 0.17, p < 0.01$) and to positively moderate the relationship between PDC and operational performance ($b = 0.23, p < 0.001$). Accordingly, $H3$ is supported. These results (Figure 3) show that PDC improves an SME's operational performance when competitive turbulence is high, while in environments where competitive turbulence is low, PDC reduces that operational performance.

Technological turbulence proved to be positively associated with operational performance ($b = 0.16, p < 0.05$), but it does not moderate the relationship between PDC and operational performance; thus, $H4$ is not supported. Market turbulence could not be tested because of the measure's reliability issues; therefore, $H5$ could not be tested.

Dependent variable: Operational performance Model 1 Model 2

Control variables			
Company age	—	0.00	0.00
Industry: metal manufacturing	—	0.19	0.04
Company size: over 10 me		0.12	0.02
Main effects			
PDC		—0.06	0.04
Technological turbulence		0.16 ^m	
Competitor turbulence			0.17 ^{mm}
Moderation effects			

PDC×technological turbulence	0.10	
×PDC competitor turbulence		0.23 ^{mm}
R ²	0.05	0.16
Adjusted R ²	0.02	0.13
F	1.76	5.96

Notes: ^mp < 0.05, ^{mm}p < 0.01, ^{mmm}p < 0.001

Manufacturing companies struggle to capture value flowing from digitalization. Previous studies have recognized that electronics supply chain processes influence operational performance. However, it has also been argued that the relationship between digitalization and performance is nonlinear or that the relationship may be mediated by a number of intermediate variables. Our study shows that the relationship between PDC and performance varies depending on the prevailing environmental conditions. Prior studies have demonstrated that digitalization may have a positive effect, a negative effect, or no direct effect on performance. Our results show that PDC in and of itself does not affect operational performance; however, when the moderating effect of environmental turbulence is factored in, PDC may benefit firms in various ways. Hence, this study offers valuable information about the impact of digitalization on firm performance from the interorganizational perspective. In addition, this study contributes to the prior research by offering one possible explanation for the diverse results of studies of digitalization on firm performance. Environmental turbulence positively moderates the relationship between PDC and SMEs' operational performance, meaning that in a turbulent environment, the effects of PDC on operational performance are positive.

Managerial implications

The results highlight that adopting digital technologies, platforms or tools is not a guaranteed route to competitive advantage, operational efficiency or success. Digitalization-related capabilities must be developed to use the opportunities presented by various tools and techniques. When adopting digital platforms and building digital connectivity between firms, managers should consider the skills required to use those tools.

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